

Radial Basis Function (RBF)

INTRODUCTION

The Radial Basis Function (RBF) is a meshfree method used to construct an interpolated function that fits a curve. This approach is commonly referred to as the Radial Point Interpolation Method (RPIM) and is often considered within the scope of the Point Interpolation Method (PIM) in many meshfree books. Similar to the PIM, the RPIM is capable of fitting the curve exactly, meaning that the fitted function passes through all of the given nodes, as illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1

To establish the RPIM formulation, we start with a representation of a curve function, $f(x)$, in 1D system using RBF, given by:

$$f(x) = a_1 R_1(x) + a_2 R_2(x) + a_3 R_3(x) + \dots + a_n R_n(x) \quad \dots(1)$$

where x is the spatial variable, a_1 - a_n are constants, $R_1(x)$ - $R_n(x)$ are the radial basis functions (this will be discussed later) and n is the number of RBF terms required.

Equation (1) can be represented in a matrix form as:

$$f(x) = \{R_1(x) \ R_2(x) \ R_3(x) \ \dots \ R_n(x)\} \begin{Bmatrix} a_1 \\ a_2 \\ a_3 \\ \vdots \\ a_n \end{Bmatrix} = \mathbf{R}^T \mathbf{a} \quad \dots(2)$$

or, can also be written in a typical meshfree form as:

$$f(x) = \sum_{i=1}^n R_i(x) a_i \quad \dots(3)$$

where i is the running index, $R_i(x)$ is a set of RBFs and a_i is a set of constants, which are unknowns to be solved.

DIFFERENT TYPES OF RBF

Going back to the RBF terms, $R_i(x)$, in practice, there are several types of RBF that can be used to fit a curve. Before looking into that, it is useful to first define a 'distance function', r_i , as all the RBFs use it in their equation. For 1D problem, r_i can simply be defined as:

$$r_i = |x - x_i|, \quad i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n \quad (4)$$

where x is the reference node and x_i are all other nodes in the system, as illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2

The value of r_i will then be used in the computation of the RBFs, as follows.

1) MQ

$$R_i(x) = (r_i^2 + c^2)^q, \quad i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n \quad \dots(5)$$

(c, q are the shape parameters)

2) Gaussian

$$R_i(x) = e^{-cr_i^2}, \quad i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n \quad \dots(6)$$

(c is the shape parameters)

3) TPS

$$R_i(x) = r_i^q, \quad i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n \quad \dots(7)$$

(q is the shape parameters)

4) Logarithmic RBF

$$R_i(x) = r_i^q \log r_i, \quad i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n \quad \dots(8)$$

(q is the shape parameters)

As will be shown later, the shape parameters play a crucial role in controlling the smoothness of the fitted curve, as will be demonstrated later. The differences between the four RBFs discussed above will be illustrated through a calculation example, which is presented next.

EXAMPLE OF CURVE FITTING

Let say we have a set of known nodes along a curve, u_c , given as:

$$u_c^T = \{u_1 \ u_2 \ u_3 \ \dots \ u_k\} \quad \dots(9)$$

where k is the number of available curve nodes. For the sake of simplicity, let us consider only 5 nodes, u_1 - u_5 , located at specific x_c coordinates, as shown in the codes:

```
clear, clc
n = 5 % number of given nodes
```

```
n = 5
```

```
uc = [0 1.25 1 -0.5 0]' % nodal values of a curve
```

```
uc = 5x1
    0
    1.2500
    1.0000
   -0.5000
    0
```

```
xc = [0 1 2 3.5 5]' % location (x-axis)
```

```
xc = 5x1
    0
    1.0000
    2.0000
    3.5000
    5.0000
```

```
plot(xc,uc,'rx','MarkerSize',10,'LineWidth',2)
axis equal
box off
```

We are going to fit these nodes using the RPIM approach. First, we link each nodal value that we have to the fitted function given in equation (2). For example, we use a general form, that is, when $x = x_1$, $f(x) = u_1$, thus yields:

$$u_1 = \{R_1(x_1) \ R_2(x_1) \ R_3(x_1) \ R_4(x_1) \ R_5(x_1)\} \begin{Bmatrix} a_1 \\ a_2 \\ a_3 \\ a_4 \\ a_5 \end{Bmatrix} \dots(10)$$

This will give us one equation. Doing this for all nodes, we will obtain 5 equations, which can be put in a matrix form as given by:

$$\begin{bmatrix} R_1(x_1) & R_2(x_1) & R_3(x_1) & R_4(x_1) & R_5(x_1) \\ R_1(x_2) & R_2(x_2) & R_3(x_2) & R_4(x_2) & R_5(x_2) \\ R_1(x_3) & R_2(x_3) & R_3(x_3) & R_4(x_3) & R_5(x_3) \\ R_1(x_4) & R_2(x_4) & R_3(x_4) & R_4(x_4) & R_5(x_4) \\ R_1(x_5) & R_2(x_5) & R_3(x_5) & R_4(x_5) & R_5(x_5) \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} a_1 \\ a_2 \\ a_3 \\ a_4 \\ a_5 \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} u_1 \\ u_2 \\ u_3 \\ u_4 \\ u_5 \end{Bmatrix} \quad \dots(11)$$

It is important to note that in the RPIM, the number of unknowns must be equal to the number of given nodes. Equation (11) can be written in a simple form as:

$$\mathbf{R}_c \mathbf{a} = \mathbf{u}_c \quad \dots(12)$$

where $\mathbf{R}_c$ is a matrix of RBFs evaluated at the 5 nodal locations and $\mathbf{u}_c$ is a vector of nodal values.

Now, $\mathbf{a}$ can be solved by:

$$\mathbf{a} = \mathbf{R}_c^{-1} \mathbf{u}_c \quad \dots(13)$$

Assuming that $\mathbf{a}$ is now solved. By inserting it back into equation (2), the general fitted function can be given as:

$$f(x) = \mathbf{R}^T (\mathbf{R}_c^{-1} \mathbf{u}_c) \quad \dots(14)$$

or can also be rearranged to yield:

$$f(x) = (\mathbf{R}^T \mathbf{R}_c^{-1}) \mathbf{u}_c = \Phi \mathbf{u}_c \quad \dots(15)$$

where Φ can be called as a matrix of shape functions. A typical form of meshfree for equation (10) is:

$$f(x) = \sum_{i=1}^n \phi_i(x) u_i \quad \dots(16)$$

in which:

$$\phi_i(x) = \left\{ R_1(x) \ R_2(x) \ R_3(x) \ R_4(x) \ R_5(x) \right\} \begin{bmatrix} R_1(x_1) & R_2(x_1) & R_3(x_1) & R_4(x_1) & R_5(x_1) \\ R_1(x_2) & R_2(x_2) & R_3(x_2) & R_4(x_2) & R_5(x_2) \\ R_1(x_3) & R_2(x_3) & R_3(x_3) & R_4(x_3) & R_5(x_3) \\ R_1(x_4) & R_2(x_4) & R_3(x_4) & R_4(x_4) & R_5(x_4) \\ R_1(x_5) & R_2(x_5) & R_3(x_5) & R_4(x_5) & R_5(x_5) \end{bmatrix}^{-1} \quad \dots(17)$$

It is important to note that, x is a spatial variable, whilst x_1 - x_5 are the location of nodal values (as discussed earlier). Now we can say that, $f(x)$ is a continuous interpolated function along x , based on a given nodal values (u_1 - u_5) at specified locations (x_1 - x_5).

The implementation codes for these steps are given here:

1) First, we calculate the $\mathbf{R}_c$ matrix (we use RBF-MQ for a demo):

```
Rc = [];
c = 0; q = 1.2; %shape parameters
for i = 1:n
    ri = abs(xc(i)-xc(1:5)'); % in a vector 1x5
    Rci = (ri.^2 + c^2).^q; % RBF-MQ
    Rc = cat(1,Rc,Rci); % generate the Pc matrix
end
```

```
Rc
```

```
Rc = 5x5
      0    1.0000    5.2780    20.2192    47.5913
    1.0000      0    1.0000    9.0169    27.8576
    5.2780    1.0000      0    2.6462    13.9666
   20.2192    9.0169    2.6462      0    2.6462
   47.5913   27.8576   13.9666    2.6462      0
```

2) In order to produce a continuous fitted curve, we create a spatial variable, x , ranging from 0 to 5 (with a step of 0.1).

```
x = 0:0.1:5
```

```
x = 1x51
      0    0.1000    0.2000    0.3000    0.4000    0.5000    0.6000    0.7000    0.8000    0.90
```

3) Now we can obtain the shape function matrix given in equation (17):

```
R = [];
for i = 1:length(x)
    ri = abs(x(i)-xc(1:5)'); % in a vector 1x5
    Ri = (ri.^2 + c^2).^q; % RBF-MQ
    R = cat(1,R,Ri); % generate the Pc matrix
end
phi = R/Rc
```

```
phi = 51x5
    1.0000      0      0      0      0
    0.8678    0.1553   -0.0242    0.0189   -0.0085
    0.7398    0.3067   -0.0493    0.0320   -0.0141
    0.6172    0.4509   -0.0727    0.0400   -0.0173
    0.5010    0.5848   -0.0923    0.0437   -0.0183
    0.3923    0.7056   -0.1061    0.0434   -0.0175
    0.2920    0.8104   -0.1118    0.0398   -0.0154
    0.2013    0.8963   -0.1071    0.0332   -0.0121
    0.1212    0.9596   -0.0894    0.0241   -0.0082
    0.0534    0.9963   -0.0554    0.0130   -0.0040
```

4) By multiplying the shape function matrix with the nodal values (uc), we obtain the fitted curve:

```
fx = phi*uc
```

```
fx = 51x1
      0
    0.1604
```

```
0.3181
0.4709
0.6168
0.7542
0.8814
0.9966
1.0981
```

```
cla
plot(xc,uc,'rx','MarkerSize',10,'LineWidth',2)
hold on
plot(x,fx,'b--')
hold off
axis equal
box off
```

GENERALISED CODES

Here, we provide a more generalised version of the RBF codes that allows for a flexible number of given curve nodes, adjustable parameter values, and easy evaluation of the PIM performance in curve fitting.

```
clear, clc
uc = [0 -0.8 4.8 2 -1 0 0 -4.7 2 1 0]' % nodal values of a curve
```

```
uc = 11x1
```

```
0
0.0000
```

```
-0.8000
 4.8000
 2.0000
-1.0000
  0
  0
-4.7000
 2.0000
 1.0000
```

```
n = length(uc) % number of given nodes
```

```
n = 11
```

```
xc = [0:(n-1)]' % x coordinates (assumed uniform)
```

```
xc = 11x1
  0
  1
  2
  3
  4
  5
  6
  7
  8
  9
```

```
% types of RBF (choose only on)
c = 0; q = 2.01; %shape parameters
f_RBF =@(ri) (ri.^2 + c^2).^q; % RBF-MQ
% f_RBF =@(ri) exp(-c*ri.^2); % RBF-EXP
% f_RBF =@(ri) ri.^q; % RBF-TPS
% f_RBF =@(ri) (ri.^q).*log10(ri+0.00001); % RBF-LOG
```

```
Rc = [];
for i = 1:n
    ri = abs(xc(i)-xc'); % in a vector 1x5
    Rci = f_RBF(ri); % RBF
    Rc = cat(1,Rc,Rci); % generate the Pc matrix
end
```

```
Rc
```

```
Rc = 11x11
```

```
104 ×
```

```
  0  0.0001  0.0016  0.0083  0.0263  0.0645  0.1343  0.2496  0.4270  0.6000  0.7600
```

```

0.0001      0      0.0001      0.0016      0.0083      0.0263      0.0645      0.1343      0.2496      0.4270      0.6856
0.0016      0.0001      0      0.0001      0.0016      0.0083      0.0263      0.0645      0.1343      0.2496      0.4270
0.0083      0.0016      0.0001      0      0.0001      0.0016      0.0083      0.0263      0.0645      0.1343      0.2496
0.0263      0.0083      0.0016      0.0001      0      0.0001      0.0016      0.0083      0.0263      0.0645      0.1343
0.0645      0.0263      0.0083      0.0016      0.0001      0      0.0001      0.0016      0.0083      0.0263      0.0645
0.1343      0.0645      0.0263      0.0083      0.0016      0.0001      0      0.0001      0.0016      0.0083      0.0263
0.2496      0.1343      0.0645      0.0263      0.0083      0.0016      0.0001      0      0.0001      0.0016      0.0083
0.4270      0.2496      0.1343      0.0645      0.0263      0.0083      0.0016      0.0001      0      0.0001      0.0016
0.6856      0.4270      0.2496      0.1343      0.0645      0.0263      0.0083      0.0016      0.0001      0.0001      0.0016

```

```

dxc = 0.1; % step (can be changed if necessary)
x = min(xc):dxc:max(xc) % interpolation locations

```

```

x = 1x101
      0      0.1000      0.2000      0.3000      0.4000      0.5000      0.6000      0.7000      0.8000      0.9000

```

```

R = [];
for i = 1:length(x)
    ri = abs(x(i)-xc'); % in a vector 1x5
    Ri = f_RBF(ri); % RBF
    R = cat(1,R,Ri); % generate the Pc matrix
end
phi = R/Rc

```

```

phi = 101x11
      1.0000      0      0      0      0      0      0      0      0      0
      0.8349      0.2478     -0.1069      0.0356     -0.0143      0.0047     -0.0036      0.0034     -0.0115      0.01
      0.6850      0.4617     -0.1905      0.0639     -0.0255      0.0084     -0.0061      0.0056     -0.0186      0.02
      0.5501      0.6420     -0.2503      0.0843     -0.0333      0.0110     -0.0076      0.0068     -0.0221      0.03
      0.4300      0.7889     -0.2860      0.0967     -0.0378      0.0127     -0.0083      0.0071     -0.0227      0.03
      0.3243      0.9027     -0.2973      0.1007     -0.0391      0.0132     -0.0082      0.0068     -0.0211      0.02
      0.2328      0.9838     -0.2843      0.0963     -0.0371      0.0126     -0.0075      0.0059     -0.0178      0.02
      0.1550      1.0330     -0.2471      0.0836     -0.0319      0.0109     -0.0062      0.0046     -0.0135      0.01
      0.0907      1.0511     -0.1864      0.0627     -0.0238      0.0082     -0.0044      0.0032     -0.0088      0.01
      0.0392      1.0395     -0.1034      0.0345     -0.0130      0.0045     -0.0023      0.0016     -0.0042      0.00

```

```

fx = phi*uc

```

```

fx = 101x1
      0
     -0.6486
     -1.1678
     -1.5581
     -1.8197
     -1.9535
     -1.9607
     -1.8438
     -1.6069
     -1.2560

```

```
cla
plot(xc,uc,'rx','MarkerSize',10,'LineWidth',2)
hold on
plot(x,fx,'b--')
hold off
box off
```

REMARKS

The RPIM employs RBFs to interpolate between nodal values, and there are at least four types of RBFs used in the literature. One of the key differences between RPIM and PIM is that RPIM does not guarantee the reproduction of polynomial functions since most RBFs use the 'radial-basis-power-law' method to fit the curve. Efforts have been made to combine RBF with conventional PIM, leading to a better curve-fitting approach, which will be explained in the next topic.